

The state and quality of initial teacher education and teacher professional development research: A meta systematic mapping review

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This meta systematic mapping review explores the nature and scope of evidence syntheses on initial teacher education (ITE) and continuing professional development (CPD), with the aim to identify the topics and types of reviews being conducted, key directions for future research, and to appraise their methodological quality. The review synthesises evidence syntheses (e.g., systematic reviews) indexed in the Web of Science, Scopus, ProQuest, EBSCOHost, Google Scholar and OpenAlex. Items were included if they were a form of evidence synthesis with a methods section, focused on ITE or CPD in early childhood, primary or secondary educational contexts, and published in English between 2013 and 31 July 2025. 442 publications were included for data extraction and synthesis, predominantly comprising systematic reviews (65.0%) and focused on CPD (73.6%). Quality assessment found that 82.6% of the reviews were at least medium quality, while 15.1% were low and 2.3% critically low. Research gap analysis suggested a need for more rigorous and longitudinal primary research to be undertaken, with an increased focus on the impact of ITE and CPD on student outcomes, including a wider range of participant populations. Suggestions are provided to guide policymakers, professional learning educators, and future primary and secondary research.

Keywords: pre-service teachers, K-12, early childhood education, systematic review, professional learning, professional learning communities, research practice integration

1. Introduction

Initial Teacher Education (ITE) and Continuing Professional Development (CPD) for in-service teachers¹ are complementary pillars of teacher learning that together shape teacher effectiveness, professional identity, and student² outcomes. High-quality ITE equips pre-service teachers (PSTs) with foundational content knowledge, pedagogical skills, and the ability to integrate theory with classroom practice, while fostering reflective practice, self-efficacy, and professional commitment (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017; Ingersoll & Strong,

¹ The term ‘teachers’ in this article refers to both classroom teachers and school leaders.

² The term ‘students’ in this article refers to school pupils.

2011). CPD builds on this foundation by supporting teachers' ongoing professional learning, intended to update knowledge, refine instructional strategies, and respond to evolving curricular and technological demands (Timperley et al., 2007). Together, ITE and CPD are intended to form a continuous professional learning continuum, preparing teachers not only at the start of their careers but throughout their professional lives, ultimately supporting both instructional quality and systemic educational improvement (MacPhail et al., 2022).

A comprehensive and thorough evaluation of the professional learning landscape is a fundamental step towards ensuring the development and implementation of ITE and CPD that is both fit for purpose and contextually relevant (Kennedy, 2016). Such evaluations help identify potential structural barriers to implementation and verify whether professional learning programmes are yielding the intended impact on teacher and student outcomes (Guskey, 2002). Given the proliferation of diverse professional learning models within teacher education and increasingly complex school contexts, as well as ongoing discussions around the methodological quality of PD research (e.g., Asterhan & Lefstein, 2024; Sims & Fletcher-Wood, 2021), there is a critical need for a mapping review to clarify the current state of research, identify enduring gaps in understanding, and contribute evidence-informed suggestions for policy and practice.

1.1 Evidence synthesis quality in Education

The field of Education has a growing tradition of using evidence syntheses, such as systematic reviews and meta-analyses, to inform evidence-based practice and policy, with the aim of improving educational outcomes (Slavin, 2020). However, the number of reviews being undertaken has the potential to create 'research waste' when multiple syntheses are conducted on overlapping or similar topics (Grainger et al., 2020). To overcome this risk, it is useful to conduct meta reviews (e.g., Bond et al., 2024), sometimes referred to as an 'overview of reviews', a 'review of reviews' (Sutton et al., 2019), or a 'tertiary review' (Kitchenham et al., 2009). A meta review combines the findings from different types of evidence synthesis on similar topics³, as opposed to traditional secondary reviews that investigate primary studies. The purpose is to provide a higher-level overview and critical assessment of the existing review landscape on a given topic, in order to highlight areas of consensus or discrepancy, address quality and methodological rigour, and ultimately to ensure that the best evidence is readily available to policy, funders and school-based decision makers.

A growing number of education meta reviews exploring evidence synthesis quality have been published in the last three years, including widening participation in higher education (Negrea & Gartland, 2025), educational technology (Bond, 2024; Buntins et al., 2023; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2025), programming and robotics (Forsström et al., 2024), and AI in higher education (Bond et al., 2024). As they used similar approaches and questions to assess methodological rigour of the included reviews, it is possible to compare their findings (see Appendix A).

³ It should be noted that 'umbrella reviews' are a type of meta review that only synthesises systematic reviews.

Although there are some clear differences between them in a few cases, reviews tend to include clear research questions, aims or objectives, the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and publication years of included primary studies. However, transparency issues are common. These include not providing the full search string, not reporting inter-rater reconciliation processes, not providing the full data extraction coding scheme, not conducting a quality assessment of primary studies when it is required (e.g., systematic reviews), not providing sufficient details about included studies (e.g., in a summary table), and not reflecting deeply on methodological limitations. For example, out of 361 EdTech reviews, Buntins et al. (2023) found that only 16 were fully replicable, and only 8.1% of 576 reviews assessed by Zawacki-Richter et al. (2025) achieved a quality score above 90/100.

1.2 Previous meta syntheses of teacher education professional development

Although the number of reviews in education has increased significantly over time, meta reviews in teacher education remain scarce and vary in quality (see Table 1), including those that do not identify themselves as such in their title (e.g., Eadie et al., 2024). Cordingley et al. (2015) sought to inform ongoing policy reviews being undertaken in England by identifying evidence about effective teacher CPD published between 2000 and 2012. They found that professional development is most effective when it lasts more than two school terms, provides iterative opportunities for consolidation and repetition, and is relevant to its participants. Additional features identified as being effective included external input, peer support, a shared sense of purpose, as well as a focus on both pedagogy and subject knowledge. However, this umbrella review included only nine reviews. Similarly, the systematic review by du Plooy et al. (2016) synthesised the findings of only three systematic reviews to inform the design of an ITE programme. They reported that language and literacy skills development should be prioritised, learning programmes should be structured thematically and sequentially, a strong focus should be placed on the development of relationship building and goal sharing, as well as developing PSTs parental involvement skills.

Van Mieghem et al. (2020)'s meta review synthesised the findings of 26 reviews on inclusive education in mainstream primary or secondary schools, published between 2017 and 2020 across both ITE and CPD. They found that training programmes on specific student needs or disabilities were more effective than general inclusion programmes, and that professional learning should include tools and strategies that are directly related to teacher concerns and their specific context. Wohlfart and Wagner's (2023) umbrella review included 23 systematic reviews exploring teachers' digital literacy development and integration in the classroom, published up to 2020. Modelling, teacher collaboration, authentic learning situations and reflective practices were found to have a positive impact on teacher outcomes, including their perceptions and level of digital use. The umbrella review by König et al. (2023) offered a more overarching view of research on PD, exploring which theoretical frameworks, outcome measures for effectiveness, effective characteristics, and central research gaps had been identified in teaching/teacher effectiveness research. From a synthesis of 27 reviews published between 1993 and 2023, they identified teacher competence as the most used measure for effectiveness, and coursework as the most dominant process for both ITE and CPD. Finally,

the scoping review by Eadie et al. (2024) included 16 meta-analyses and systematic reviews investigating PD, which indicated promising although mixed results. PD was found to be most effective when it was integrated into practice, such as coaching, and included modelling and performance feedback.

Although these six meta reviews have provided some insight into the synthesis of teacher education research, their methodological quality was largely either low or medium as per the Quality of Evidence Synthesis Tool (Bond, 2025), relying on a very limited number of databases and a relatively small number of reviews, with the exception of Eadie et al.'s (2024) comprehensive search. Furthermore, only two reviews (du Plooy et al., 2016; Eadie et al., 2024) specifically included early childhood education, and the range of topics included were rather limited. Therefore, this article reports a meta review aiming to critically analyse and synthesise interventions and approaches across both ITE and CPD, from a wide range of evidence syntheses. Unlike previous meta reviews, it takes an inclusive approach by considering reviews focused on PSTs, teachers and school leaders across diverse educational contexts, methodologies and research designs. This broader scope not only deepens insights into the state of teacher education research, but it also seeks to inform an agenda for future primary and secondary research.

Table 1. Previous meta reviews of teacher education research

Authors	Years included	# Reviews included	Topic	Professional Level	Education Level	Quality	Platforms searched
Cordingley et al.	2000 - 2012	9	General CPD	CPD only	Primary & Secondary	Medium	First Search, JSTOR, Google Scholar
du Plooy et al.	1980 - 2011	3	General ITE & CPD	ITE & CPD	Early Childhood & Primary	Low	Google, Google Scholar
Eadie et al.	2015-2020	16	General CPD	ITE & CPD	Early Childhood	High	ERIC, ProQuest, PsycINFO, Education Research Complete, A+ Education, Web of Science, Google Scholar
König et al.	1993 - 2023	27	General ITE & CPD	ITE & CPD	Primary & Secondary	Medium	Web of Science, ERIC
van Mieghem et al.	2017 - 2020	26	Inclusive education	ITE & CPD	Primary & Secondary	Low	Web of Science, ERIC
Wolfhart & Wagner	2006 - 2020	23	Digital competencies	ITE & CPD	Primary & Secondary	High	EBSCOHost, ERIC, journals

1.3 Research questions

This meta review seeks to answer the following questions:

- (1) When, where, and with whom has research on ITE and CPD been conducted?
- (2) What types of evidence syntheses have been conducted on ITE and CPD and what are the sample sizes?
- (3) What is the quality of existing ITE and CPD reviews?

- (4) What topics and interventions in ITE and CPD have been reviewed over the past decade?
- (5) What research gaps have been identified in ITE and CPD secondary research?

2. Methodology

To address the above research questions and inform the development of an online Evidence Toolkit for professional development leads⁴, a meta systematic mapping review was conducted using a tertiary method (Bond et al., 2024; Kitchenham et al., 2009), following best practice guidance (e.g., Khalil et al., 2025). A protocol was developed in conjunction with an International Advisory Board, comprising key external stakeholders including substantive and methodological experts, and published prior to starting the review (Chong et al., 2024), which outlined explicit and predefined criteria that would guide the review process (Gough et al., 2012). The reporting here is guided by PRISMA (Page et al., 2021) and PRISMA-S (Rethlefsen et al., 2021), as well as the Quality of Evidence Synthesis Tool (Bond, 2025). All search strategy information including PRISMA checklists and further search strings can be found on the OSF⁵.

2.1 Search strategy

2.1.1 Search string

The search string (see Table 2 and OSF) was adapted from a previous tertiary review (Bond et al., 2024), in conjunction with consulting educational professionals at the National Institute of Teaching, and focuses on teacher professional development, education and variations of evidence synthesis (as per Sutton et al., 2019).

2.1.2 Searching and study selection

The first search was conducted in January 2024 in the platforms Web of Science (Core Collection), Scopus, ProQuest (ERIC), and EBSCOHost (British Education Index, Teacher Reference Center), as these have been found suitable for evidence synthesis (Gusenbauer & Haddaway, 2020). Date search parameters spanned from 1 January 2013 to 31 December 2023. African Journals Online was also searched, to capture more Global South research, although no further studies were identified. Google Scholar was searched additionally, using the software Publish or Perish (Harzing, 2007) and the modified search strings ("teacher professional development" AND "systematic review"), ("teacher training" AND "systematic review"), and ("teacher education" AND "systematic review"), limiting maximum results to 1000. Citation and bibliography searching, as well as bidirectional checking of bi-citations and recommendations, was then undertaken within the OpenAlex platform (Priem et al., 2022). This was conducted after screening on both the title and abstract and screening on full text stages to identify further literature, alongside manual searching of relevant organisational

⁴ <https://evidenceportal.niot.org.uk/toolkit/>

⁵ https://osf.io/3zmtc/overview?view_only=162cd00900d447c4958bd146059509ab

websites (i.e., The Education Endowment Foundation, Campbell Collaboration, National Institute of Teaching). The OpenAlex platform indexes approximately 209 million publications and was accessed through EPPI Reviewer evidence synthesis software (Thomas et al., 2024). To ensure that the review is as up to date as possible, additional searches in the same databases were conducted up to 31 July 2025.

Table 2. Search string

Category	Terms
Teacher professional learning	("professional development" OR "teacher training" OR "initial teacher education" OR "teacher preparation" OR "continu* professional development" OR "pre-service teacher" OR "preservice teacher" OR "in-service teacher" OR "student teacher" OR "teacher professional learning" OR "teacher professional education" OR "INSET" OR "in-service education and training")
AND	
Education sector	("higher education" OR college* OR universit* OR undergrad* OR graduat* OR postgrad* OR "K-12" OR school* OR kindergarten* OR "primary school*" OR "middle school*" OR "high school*" OR "elementary school*" OR "secondary school*" OR "nursery school*" OR "early years" OR "early childhood education")
AND	
Evidence synthesis	("systematic review" OR "scoping review" OR "narrative review" OR "meta-analysis" OR "evidence synthesis" OR "meta-review" OR "evidence map" OR "rapid review" OR "umbrella review" OR "qualitative synthesis" OR "configurative review" OR "aggregative review" OR "thematic synthesis" OR "framework synthesis" OR "mapping review" OR "meta-synthesis" OR "qualitative evidence synthesis" OR "critical review" OR "integrative review" OR "integrative synthesis" OR "narrative summary" OR "state of the art review" OR "rapid evidence assessment" OR "qualitative research synthesis" OR "qualitative metasummary" OR "meta-ethnography" OR "meta-narrative review" OR "mixed methods synthesis" OR "scoping study" OR "systematic map")

2.1.3 Inclusion/exclusion criteria and screening

The search strategy yielded 8,231 items (see Figure 1), which were exported as .txt or .ris files from each platform and imported into EPPI Reviewer (Thomas et al., 2024). Following automatic removal of duplicates within the software, five reviewers screened the same 200 items on title and abstract (2 x 100), applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria (see Table 3) to try to achieve inter-rater reliability. Studies were included if they were a form of evidence synthesis with a method section (e.g., systematic review), focused on initial teacher education, in-service teacher continuing professional development or both at the pre-primary (early childhood), primary or secondary level, and published in English between 2013 and July 2025. Reviews that solely focused on paraprofessionals were excluded, as were bibliometric reviews and Masters theses. The decision to only include English language publications was made due to the time restrictions of the project.

After screening the initial 200 items, a Fleiss kappa of 0.67 was reached and, whilst this is considered substantial (Landis & Koch, 1977), the cautious decision was made to screen all remaining items in duplicate using the priority screening function within EPPI Reviewer, after

the initial disagreements had been reconciled. Priority screening uses machine learning, which is trained using selected include and exclude codes, which then identifies those items that are more likely to be included and presents them to reviewers first. In this case, the algorithm was trained using the codes ‘EXCLUDE not evidence synthesis with a methods section and synthesised findings’, ‘EXCLUDE not about teacher CPD or ITE’ and ‘INCLUDE on full text’. Each item was then screened by two reviewers, with disagreements resolved by a third reviewer.

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram

Table 3. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Published 2013 to 31 July 2025	Published before Jan 2013 or after July 2025
Initial teacher education and/or in-service teacher continued professional development	Solely focused on paraprofessionals
Pre-primary, primary or secondary	Higher education, vocational education
A form of evidence synthesis, including umbrella reviews	Primary research, reviews with no formal method section, Masters thesis, bibliometric reviews, theoretical articles, editorials
English language	In a language other than English

After all items were screened on title and abstract, 671 PDFs were retrieved to be screened on full text. To continue minimising bias at the full text stage, two rounds of blind screening 50 items were conducted among four reviewers achieving a Fleiss kappa of 0.66, and the decision was again made to double screen all remaining 571 in duplicate, with any disagreements

resolved through a third reviewer and discussion among the review team. This identified 442 evidence syntheses for inclusion and data extraction.

2.2 Data extraction

The data extraction coding tool (see OSF⁶) was adapted from that used by Bond et al. (2024) and developed in conjunction with the International Advisory Board. To ensure relevance to practice, some predetermined topics or foci were elicited from the National Institute of Teaching team as well as a recent sector-wide research consultation to inform the deductive coding process (National Institute of Teaching, 2024). Extracted data included publication and authorship information (e.g., open access status, author country affiliations), review type (e.g., systematic review), any special focus of the review (e.g., geographical or subject specific focus), whether it related to ITE or CPD and which education level if applicable, training or topic focus, countries and World Bank regions of the primary studies included, methodological characteristics (e.g., databases searched), key findings and research gaps. All data were manually captured and input into EPPI Reviewer.

Owing to the heterogenous nature of the evidence syntheses included in the review, many of the data were captured using inductive coding, including the training or topic focus (e.g., flipped classroom) and research gaps (e.g., bigger sample sizes needed). The key findings were inductively coded under subheadings indicating whether CPD features had a positive, negative, limited or neutral impact on teachers and students, as well as identifying which outcomes were influenced, although this will not be reported in the present mapping review and will instead be the focus of future systematic reviews. Research gaps as identified and reported by review authors were inductively coded under subheadings within either ‘Methodological gaps’ (e.g., bigger sample sizes needed) or ‘Topic research gaps’ (e.g., lesson planning). An initial five studies were coded by six members of the review team and discussed at length, to ensure agreement and common understanding of the coding scheme, before the remaining items were single coded between reviewers.

2.3 Quality assessment

The quality of ITE and CPD reviews was assessed using version 1 of the Quality of Evidence Synthesis Assessment Tool (QuEST, Bond, 2025), which was adapted from the AMSTAR 2 (Shea et al., 2017) and DARE tools (Centre for Reviews and Dissemination (UK), 1995; Lai & Bower, 2020). The version of QuEST used here consists of 10 questions, which are scored as per previous reviews (e.g., Buntins et al., 2023; L. Tran et al., 2021): Yes = 1, Partly = 0.5 and No = 0 (see Table 4). Where evidence synthesis types did not require a quality assessment on a given question (e.g., scoping and mapping reviews, see Sutton et al., 2019), these were coded ‘Not Applicable’ and scored 1. It should also be noted that the quality appraisal was not used to eliminate studies from the corpus, but rather to answer research question three. A total score was calculated out of 10 and items were determined as critically low (0-2.5), low (3-4.5),

⁶ https://osf.io/3zmtc/overview?view_only=162cd00900d447c4958bd146059509ab

medium (5-7), high (7.5-8.5) or excellent (9-10) quality, as used in other reviews (e.g., Urdaneta-Ponte et al., 2021). An initial five papers were assessed by six members of the review team to achieve consistency through discussion. To ensure coding consistency, 30 reviews were double screened by two members of the research team, reaching 90% agreement. Quality assessment for the remaining papers was then carried out independently by two members of the research team, with a third reviewer conducting a quality appraisal of five random items from each of the ‘critically low’, ‘low’, ‘high’ and ‘excellent’ categories. The quality of only one study was disagreed upon, but consensus was reached after discussion.

Table 4. Quality assessment criteria (QuEST; Bond et al., 2024)

Criterion	Score	Interpretation
RQs	Yes	RQs, aims or objectives are explicitly and clearly defined.
	Partly	Some mention of objectives or aims are alluded to.
	No	No RQs, aims or objectives are identifiable.
Inclusion/exclusion	Yes	The criteria used are explicitly defined in the paper.
	Partly	The criteria are implicit.
	No	The criteria are not defined and cannot be readily inferred.
Publication years	Yes	The publication years are clearly stated, e.g. 2010-2020.
	Partly	The publication years state from a year OR until a year.
	No	The publication years are not defined at all.
Search coverage	Yes	4 or more digital libraries searched and included additional search strategies (e.g. snowballing) OR identified and referenced all pertinent journals.
	Partly	3 or 4 digital libraries searched with no extra search strategies OR searched a defined but restricted set of journals and conference proceedings.
	No	2 digital libraries searched or an extremely restricted set of journals.
Search string	Yes	The search string was reported in full and is replicable.
	Partly	Examples of keywords only were given.
	No	The search terms were not provided in any form.
Inter-rater reliability	Yes	An inter-rater reliability value is reported (e.g. Cohen’s kappa).
	Partly	Mention is made of how disagreements were reconciled.
	No	No inter-rater reliability is mentioned.
Data extraction	Yes	The full coding scheme was provided.
	Partly	Examples are provided, but not the full list.
	No	The coding scheme was not provided at all.
Quality assessment	Yes	Explicitly defined quality criteria extracted for each study.
	Partly	The research question involved quality issues that are addressed by the study.
	No	No explicit quality assessment of individual papers has been attempted.
Study description	Yes	Information is presented about each paper.
	Partly	Only summary information is presented about individual papers.
	No	The results for individual studies are not specified.
Review limitations	Yes	Yes, there is a specific identifiable limitations section.
	Partly	There is some mention of limitations.
	No	There is no limitations section or reflection on limitations

2.4 Narrative synthesis and interactive gap map development

A narrative synthesis of the data was undertaken (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006), combined with systematic mapping to synthesise the review results into themes (see OSF⁷). A combination of inductive and deductive coding was used to synthesise the charted information, guided by the iterative process of coding in grounded theory (Charmaz, 2006). The data captured inductively were grouped into larger subcategories during synthesis (e.g., flipped classroom was categorised under blended/online learning), to facilitate a more refined understanding and to assist with producing evidence and gap maps (EGMs) using EPPI Mapper software (Digital Solution Foundry & EPPI Centre, 2025). For example, in order to help answer research question five (What research gaps have been identified in ITE and CPD?), one EGM was created using ‘Training focus/topic’ as the columns, ‘Education Level’ as the rows, and segmented by ‘Professional Level’. This provided a visual representation of how many reviews had been undertaken focused on ITE and CPD for each topic area and each education level. To provide further visualisations of the key findings obtained in this review, an openly accessible web database⁸ of the included studies was made using EPPI Visualiser. This allows users to interact with the data through frequency and crosstabulation reports, as well as export metadata and view all coding decisions. In the final stage, the International Advisory Board provided feedback on the draft synthesis.

3. Findings

3.1 When, where and with whom has research on ITE and CPD been conducted?

3.1.1 General publication characteristics

The majority of the 442 evidence syntheses were published as journal articles (92.5%, $n = 409$), as opposed to dissertations (2.3%, $n = 10$) or book chapters (2.3%, $n = 10$); however, only 54.5% were available as open access (see Appendix B). Although the number of evidence syntheses was modest between 2013 and 2018, there has been an increasing interest, with a particularly large rise in 2022 and 2023 (see Figure 2). This was possibly due to the impact of COVID-19 on the ability of researchers to undertake primary investigations (Bond et al., 2021), as numbers almost halved in 2024. The largest number of journal articles were published in *Teaching and Teacher Education* ($n = 21$; see Appendix C), *Review of Educational Research* ($n = 14$), *Professional Development in Education* ($n = 12$), *Educational Research Review* ($n = 11$), *Education Sciences* ($n = 10$) and *Review of Education* ($n = 9$).

3.1.2 Authorship characteristics

Evidence syntheses in teacher education PD were almost always undertaken collaboratively (88.9%, $n = 393$), with teams of two (24.4%, $n = 108$) and three authors (26.0%, $n = 115$) the most common. Of those that could be identified, Education was the most predominant first author discipline (68.8%, $n = 304$), followed by Psychology (5.9%, $n = 26$), with authors

⁷ https://osf.io/3zmtc/overview?view_only=162cd00900d447c4958bd146059509ab

⁸ <https://eppi.ioe.ac.uk/epi-vis/login/open?webdbid=666>

working in 58 different countries (see Appendix D) in all continents (see Figure 3). Nearly one third of publications had at least one author from an institution in the United States (30.5%, $n = 135$), with the highest number of studies authored by European researchers (39.4%, $n = 174$).

Figure 2. Number of evidence syntheses published per year

Figure 3. Geographical distribution of authors

3.1.3 Contextual characteristics

More than half of the reviews included research at the primary/elementary school level (55.0%, $n = 243$), closely followed by secondary school research (48.6%, $n = 215$), with only 24.0% focused on Early Childhood ($n = 106$). Over one third of reviews did not specify which

education levels the primary studies were undertaken in (35.1%, $n = 155$), which limits their applicability to other contexts. Perhaps unsurprisingly, as it echoes previous research (e.g., Castanheira, 2016), almost half of the reviews were exploring CPD-only research (46.4%, $n = 205$), 28.1% of studies focused on both CPD and ITE ($n = 124$), and 26.2% of studies focused solely on ITE ($n = 116$). Only 20 reviews explicitly focused on or included primary research exploring the role of leadership in PD (e.g., Lipscombe et al., 2023) and only 22 reviews solely investigated pre-service Early Childhood educator experiences (e.g., Szocik et al., 2024).

The majority focused on PD across a variety of subjects, although there were also a small amount of subject-specific reviews (see OSF⁹), including Science (4.5%, $n = 20$; e.g., You et al., 2025), Maths (3.4%, $n = 15$; e.g., Sharma & Sharma, 2023) and Physical Education (3.4%, $n = 15$; e.g., Østerlie et al., 2025). Primary studies were included from all World Bank regions (see Appendix E), with more than half of the corpus including research from North America (62.4%, $n = 276$), East Asia & Pacific (53.8%, $n = 238$) and Europe & Central Asia (52.7%, $n = 233$). Although the other regions were substantially less represented, all but South Asia (10.0%, $n = 44$) were present in at least 20% of reviews. Almost two thirds of evidence syntheses included research from the United States (62.0%, $n = 274$; see Figure 4), with the next most frequent being Australia (37.1%, $n = 164$), Canada (28.1%, $n = 124$), UK (26.7%, $n = 118$) and Türkiye (23.5%, $n = 104$). However, 20.1% of reviews did not report within which countries the primary studies were undertaken ($n = 89$), and 14.3% of reviews mentioned some countries but did not report all of them ($n = 63$). The authors of the present meta review did not check to see the extent of primary study overlap between reviews, given the volume.

Figure 4. Geographical distribution of primary studies within reviews

⁹ https://osf.io/3zmtc/overview?view_only=162cd00900d447c4958bd146059509ab

3.2 What kinds of evidence syntheses have been conducted and what are the sample sizes?

There were 18 different types of evidence syntheses conducted (see Appendix F), as identified by their authors. Systematic reviews were by far the most popular (65.2%, $n = 288$), followed by meta-analysis (13.8%, $n = 61$) and scoping reviews (10.4%, $n = 46$). The combined rapid review and meta-analysis by Fletcher-Wood and Zuccullo (2020) was one of only a handful of sector-facing reports commissioned by funders such as the Wellcome Trust and the Education Endowment Foundation (e.g., Sims et al., 2021).

The majority of reviews included between 20-49 primary studies (44.8%) for final extraction and analysis (see Figure 5), although a quarter of them only found a maximum of 19 primary studies matching their inclusion criteria (27.4%), including a rapid review of 12 studies to explore what is known about effective PD for K-12 teachers (Cirkony et al., 2024). Despite having method sections, three evidence syntheses did not report the final number of included primary studies (Adeoye Moses Adeleke et al., 2023; Ash et al., 2025; Sari et al., 2023). Evidence syntheses with over 400 studies included a scoping review of Nordic ITE research (Forsström & Munthe, 2023), a systematic review of online ITE teaching and learning (Dyment & Downing, 2020), and a scoping review of environmental and sustainability teacher education research topics and methodologies (Blom & Karrow, 2024).

Figure 5. Number of evidence syntheses by primary study sample size

3.3 What is the quality of ITE and CPD reviews?

The majority of studies included clear research questions, aims or objectives (85.1%) and the publication years of included literature (70.1%). However, only half included full details about both inclusion and exclusion criteria (55.7%), provided a fully replicable Boolean search string (52.9%) or searched in at least four academic platforms as well as conducting additional search strategies such as citation or bibliography searching, or searching in specific conference

proceedings or journals (51.1%). 43.0% did not report any processes for establishing inter-rater reliability and understanding between coders, only 18.6% included their exact coding scheme, and 46.4% did not undertake any kind of quality assessment.

Table 5. Quality assessment for ITE & CPD corpus (n = 442)

Criteria	Yes	Partly	No	N/A
Are there clear research questions, aims or objectives?	85.1%	14.5%	0.5%	
Were inclusion AND exclusion criteria provided in the method section?	55.7%	42.3%	2.0%	
Are the publication years included defined in the title, abstract or method section?	70.1%	20.8%	9.0%	
Was the search adequately conducted and likely to have covered all relevant studies?	51.1%	31.2%	17.6%	
Was the search string reported in full?	52.9%	41.6%	4.8%	0.7%
Do they report inter-rater reliability?	29.2%	27.8%	43.0%	
Is the data extraction coding schema provided?	18.6%	58.6%	22.9%	
Is some form of quality assessment applied?	34.8%	5.4%	46.4%	13.3%
Are sufficient details provided about the individual included studies?	47.3%	25.1%	27.4%	0.2%
Is there a reflection on review limitations?	47.5%	24.9%	27.6%	

The reviews averaged a score of 6.52 out of 10 across the corpus (see Figure 7). Comparison of overall scores across time (see Appendix G) shows some improvement between 2013 to 2020, but no substantial improvement in quality since 2021. Mapping reviews and meta-analyses were more likely to be scored ‘high quality’ or ‘excellent quality’, with a wide variability of quality for systematic reviews and generally poor quality for integrative reviews, qualitative meta syntheses and umbrella reviews. Doctoral dissertations and reports (e.g. those commissioned by large funders) were predominantly ‘high’ or ‘excellent quality’, as opposed to book chapters and conference papers, half of which received a ‘low quality’ rating. Only 9% of journal articles were rated ‘excellent’ and almost a third were rated ‘high quality’ (29%).

Figure 7. Overall quality assessment

3.4 What topics and interventions in ITE and CPD have been reviewed over the past decade?

The topics of the reviews in the corpus were inductively coded by the review team and classified into 17 overarching categories and 123 subcategories (see Appendix H), with 19.7% of reviews classified as General CPD or ITE guidance ($n = 87$) without a specific focus other than ‘professional development’ or ‘teacher training’. The most frequent ‘named’ category was Equity and Inclusion (14.7%, $n = 65$), followed by Teacher Collaboration/Community (14.0%, $n = 62$), Educational Technology (13.1%, $n = 58$) and Coaching/Mentoring (8.1%, $n = 36$). However, some reviews were classified under multiple categories. For example, Sims et al. (2021) reviewed the effectiveness of teacher professional development and was therefore coded as ‘General CPD guidance’; however it was primarily focused on the effectiveness of PD within three key intervention categories (‘Coaching’, ‘Lesson Study’ and ‘Professional Learning Communities’) which it was also coded with.

3.4.1 Equity and Inclusion

Reviews focusing on the topic of Equity and Inclusion were mostly systematic reviews (68%, $n = 45$), with all but five reviews found to be of at least ‘medium quality’. They primarily explored disability inclusion through interventions across a range of disabilities (e.g., Brock & Carter, 2017), for specific regions (e.g., Asia-Pacific, Ahmed et al., 2022) and for specific subjects (e.g., physical education, Tarantino et al., 2022). Reviews also explored the design and impact of PD for supporting children with specific diagnoses such as Dyslexia (Monahan et al., 2025), ADHD (Ward et al., 2022), Autism (Marelle et al., 2025; Petersson-Bloom et al., 2023), and long-term health conditions (Hinton & Kirk, 2015), as well as exploring the teacher education experiences of disabled PSTs (Bellacicco & Demo, 2019; Strimel et al., 2023). Reviews in this category also included a large focus on culturally responsive education (e.g., Franco et al., 2023), with 13 reviews split evenly across ITE ($n = 5$) and CPD ($n = 5$), and primary and secondary levels. Inclusion reviews also explored how professional learning could affect teachers’ beliefs, attitudes and self-efficacy (e.g., Dignath et al., 2022; Khamzina et al., 2024; Wray et al., 2022). The meta-analysis by Donath et al. (2023), for example, analysed 342 studies and found that professional development had large effects on in-service teacher knowledge of inclusive behaviour ($g = 0.93$ [0.76; 1.10]) and moderate effects on teachers’ skills ($g = 0.49$ [0.41; 0.56]), but only small effects on teachers’ beliefs ($g = 0.23$ [0.17; 0.28]) and small-to-moderate effects on student behaviour ($g = 0.37$ [0.23; 0.51]). CPD that included active learning opportunities reported larger effect sizes on teachers’ skill development, and implementation quality improved when modelling was used with performance feedback.

3.4.2 Teacher Collaboration/Community

Reviews focusing on Teacher Collaboration and Community accounted for 13.8% of the total corpus ($n = 62$), with a heavy focus on CPD ($n = 56$) compared to ITE settings ($n = 20$). Across this category, 26% of reviews were classed as ‘low quality’ or ‘critically low quality’. These reviews examined a range of group-based professional learning approaches in which teachers participated collectively, with a primary focus on structured forms of collaboration. The largest

proportion of reviews addressed professional learning communities (PLCs) (6.6%, $n = 29$), including a small subset focused on online PLCs ($n = 5$). Lesson study, an approach involving structured inquiry cycles that help teachers plan, observe, and reflect collaboratively to understand and enhance student learning (e.g., Benedict et al., 2023) formed a further cluster of reviews (3.2%, $n = 14$), while a smaller number of reviews examined co-teaching models ($n = 4$), telecollaboration ($n = 3$), family or parent engagement as part of professional learning ($n = 2$), and study abroad experiences ($n = 2$). Across this body of literature, collaborative professional learning was described in varied ways, with reviews reporting considerable diversity in how collaboration was organised, sustained and conceptualised across contexts (e.g., Vangrieken et al., 2015). Differences were evident in the format, duration and focus of collaborative approaches, reflecting the breadth of interpretations of teacher collaboration represented in the literature. One review examined student voice within collaborative professional learning (Santos et al., 2024), indicating that this remains a relatively limited area of attention within the wider body of collaboration-focused reviews.

3.4.3 Educational Technology

Reviews focused on Educational Technology (EdTech; 13.1%, $n = 58$) were primarily centred on designing and delivering professional learning to develop teacher digital competencies (3.6%, $n = 16$) or the integration of technology into ITE and CPD (2.9%, $n = 13$). However, this is another topic area where ‘low quality’ and ‘critically low’ reviews have been published (19.0% of EdTech reviews). There has been far less focus on EdTech in early childhood education professional learning ($n = 4$). This is despite an OECD working paper (Dardanou et al., 2023) finding that PSTs across multiple countries continue to lack confidence in using digital tools effectively. The paper also notes that some ITE programmes focus on digital skills more generally rather than specifically on how to use tools effectively in the classroom to enhance learning, a concern reflected in the larger number of ITE focused reviews than CPD. As with many reviews in this corpus, Hennessy et al. (2022) found limited evidence of professional learning impact on teaching practice and student outcomes, although blended learning combined with reflection, coaching (including virtual coaching), and social media such as X were found to have a promising positive impact in low- and middle-income countries. Furthermore, specific EdTech tools were far less reviewed, such as artificial intelligence (e.g., Bond et al., 2025), virtual simulations (e.g., Ledger et al., 2022), augmented reality (e.g., Q. Wang & Li, 2024), 360° Video (e.g., Atal et al., 2023), ePortfolios (Harun et al., 2021), robotics (Giannandrea et al., 2021), and social media (Greenhow et al., 2020). However, this number has already increased slightly since this search was conducted (e.g., generative AI, X. Huang & Zhang, 2025).

3.4.4 Coaching/Mentoring

A total of 8.1% of reviews focused on Coaching and/or Mentoring ($n = 36$), with 13 synthesising ITE and 33 CPD research, and a much higher rate of ‘high quality’ and ‘excellent quality’ evidence syntheses (52.8%). Key strategies in ITE included bug-in-ear coaching (e.g., Gander & Dann, 2023), and virtual coaching models such as video conferencing or simulated classrooms like TeachLive (e.g., Nesje & Lejonberg, 2022). Two studies focused on mentoring

within university supervision (Burns et al., 2016; Hart, 2020), and another on mentoring within music education (Hernández-Micó & Domínguez-Lloria, 2024). Within the CPD-only context, coaching and/or mentoring were explored in 23 reviews (e.g., Reddy et al., 2025). The reviewed literature suggests that mentoring can significantly impact teacher outcomes including increased organisational awareness, improved classroom management, enhanced problem-solving skills, stronger networking abilities, higher levels of self-confidence, increased job satisfaction, and reduced turnover (Castanheira, 2016; Kraft et al., 2018; Schachter et al., 2024). Specific strategies reported as effective in promoting these positive outcomes include goal setting and performance feedback (e.g., Criss et al., 2022), online coaching (McLeod et al., 2023), and individualised one-on-one coaching (e.g., Kochmanski & Cobb, 2023). Reviews provided evidence that leadership support is essential for the success of coaching, mentoring, and collaborative initiatives (e.g., Castillo et al., 2024; Fry et al., 2025; Sims et al., 2021).

3.4.5 Teacher Competencies and Evaluation

31 reviews were classified as focusing on professional learning related to Teacher Competencies and Evaluation (7.0%), such as teacher identity formation (e.g., Swearingen, 2019), self-efficacy (e.g., Mok et al., 2023), critical thinking (e.g., J. Huang & Sang, 2023), design thinking (Blundell, 2024), and self-monitoring (Layden et al., 2023). Only one was classified as being ‘excellent quality’ (Täschner et al., 2025). Given the importance of developing professional competencies in ITE, it is perhaps unsurprising that the number of ITE reviews outweighed the number of CPD reviews. Lammert and Godfrey (2025), for example, investigated how pre-service elementary teachers are prepared for lesson planning, finding that it was rarely conducted at the programme level, thereby increasing the potential for PSTs to receive different and contradictory information from various sources. Two reviews explicitly explored the assessment of ITE competencies. Stacey et al. (2020) found that the use of video recordings of classroom practice helped PSTs to reflect on their practice, whilst also providing evidence for teacher educators. Annotating work samples for future planning and teaching was also found to deepen PST reflective processes. However, as was reported across many reviews in the wider corpus, Aparicio and Navarro-Asencio (2023) found that many studies relied on self-report data and, while PST and teacher educator perceptions are extremely important, they call for more experimental studies to be undertaken focusing on observed outcomes.

3.4.6 Blended and Online Learning

It should be noted that reviews pertaining to Emergency Remote Education (ERE) during COVID-19 were coded under ‘Education in Emergencies’ rather than here, to avoid conflating ERE with ‘business as usual’ blended and online approaches (see e.g., Bond et al., 2021). Reviews with a training focus on Blended and/or Online Learning comprised 5.7% ($n = 25$) of the sample, primarily consisting of blended learning ($n = 16$, 3.6%), including flipped learning (a specific blended learning approach, see Bond, 2020, $n = 4$), and online learning ($n = 14$, 3.2%), with considerably more ITE-specific reviews ($n = 11$) than CPD ($n = 5$). Within the ITE context, blended learning was found to positively affect PST academic performance, attitudes and self-efficacy compared to traditional teaching approaches (e.g., Ma et al., 2023). Although

many reviews highlighted continued issues with digital literacy and internet connectivity even within high income countries (e.g., Kirabo et al., 2024). Within in-service teacher PD, blended and online learning provides PD opportunities for teachers in remote areas and as such promotes collaborative learning and educational equity. However, key to engagement is course design, provision of time to conduct PD, opportunities for interaction, and access to learning support (e.g., J. Lee et al., 2021). Beach et al. (2021) emphasised the reflective nature of online PD, which can create multifaceted learning opportunities and provide ‘just-in-time’ support, including technological troubleshooting, planning, pedagogical guidance, and reflection. Mobile learning offers this potential for flexible support for both ITE and CPD, especially for those in lower-income contexts (Maliphol, 2022; Tong et al., 2023). Although De Wit and Plastow (2021) stressed the need for mobile learning content to carefully scaffold digital literacy, skills and knowledge development, and to consider infrastructure constraints and end user contexts from the beginning.

3.4.7 Health and Wellbeing

Health and Wellbeing reviews represented 4.5% ($n = 20$) of the research, with all but one being at least ‘medium quality’. There was an emphasis on mental health professional learning (1.4%, $n = 6$) for both students and teachers. Reviews stressed the need for future research to include follow-up data, report on changes in staff practice, and determine intervention feasibility across varying staff cohorts and schools (Pierret et al., 2022; Prabhu et al., 2025). Dinnen’s (2022) meta-analysis of school mental health promotion PD found a positive impact on student outcomes, including social and emotional skills and externalising problems. In a follow-up review (Dinnen et al., 2024), they identified the importance of including modelling, performance feedback, reflection and problem-solving activities, using a range of collaborative, individualised, data-driven and strengths-based approaches when designing PD. Given the increasing focus on and concerns about teacher retention (e.g., OECD, 2025), it was surprising that only two reviews were found focusing specifically on teacher wellbeing and burnout interventions (Avola et al., 2025; Cann et al., 2024). Other training foci included nutrition education (e.g., Peralta et al., 2020), as well as targeted interventions such as Physically Active Learning (e.g., Daly-Smith et al., 2021), Social and Emotional Learning (e.g., Blewitt et al., 2020), and child protection (Walsh et al., 2023).

3.4.8 Cross-Curriculum Skills

20 reviews focused on what the review team coined ‘Cross-Curriculum Skills’ (4.5%), which were predominantly exploring some form of literacy ($n = 15$) or computational thinking ($n = 5$) intervention. Seven meta-analyses analysed the impact of CPD literacy interventions, predominantly within early childhood (e.g., Brunsek et al., 2020) and primary years (e.g., Stephens, 2014), although there was one review that investigated the effect of CPD on middle and high school reading achievement (Basma & Savage, 2023). Small positive effects on student reading achievement was found in several reviews (e.g., Rice et al., 2024), although they were often linked to shorter PD duration (e.g., Basma & Savage, 2018), with calls for more in-depth investigations into the mechanisms leading to effective outcomes (e.g., Didion et al., 2020). The computational thinking reviews revealed that professional learning can help

develop teacher knowledge, confidence, and self-efficacy, particularly through game-based learning, robotics, collaboration and programming as a teaching approach (e.g., Ausiku & Matthee, 2021). However, there is a need to develop more robust tools to capture its longitudinal impact on students and teachers (Liu et al., 2024; Ortuño Meseguer & Serrano, 2023). There has also been less focus on computational thinking within ITE (Chaabi et al., 2025), and Rodrigues et al. (2024) argue that there needs to be a stronger emphasis for PSTs on the development of lesson plans and activities, including their implementation in practice, rather than just teaching theoretical concepts.

3.4.9 Teaching Strategies

A range of Teaching Strategies were the focus of 19 reviews (4.3%), with two appraised as being 'low quality'. Only one review was focused solely on Early Childhood (J. Y. Lee et al., 2025), which found that explicit modelling of reflective practices in playful learning professional development helped educators improve attitudes, knowledge, and teaching skills. Three reviews explored inquiry-based learning, two being specifically science focused (Akuma & Koenen, 2025; Strat et al., 2024) and one maths focused (Fry et al., 2025). They reported mixed outcomes, but highlighted that collaborative approaches, modelling and coaching led to more positive results. Two reviews synthesised research on differentiated instruction, with the meta-analysis by Kahmann et al. (2022) finding that PD led to improved teacher knowledge, practice and attitudes, but it had no significant effect on student learning. Langelaan et al. (2024) found that reflective practices, teacher collaboration and feedback were more likely to lead to positive effects, but that school culture and curriculum demands often acted as a barrier to successful implementation of differentiated instruction. Other teaching strategies explored were game-based learning ($n = 2$), project-based learning ($n = 2$), problem-based learning (Kirabo et al., 2024), maker education (Quintana-Ordorika et al., 2023) and dialogic teaching and learning (Xie & Lin, 2025).

3.4.10 Placement-based Learning

Placement-based Learning reviews were predominantly focused on the experiences of PSTs undertaking school-based practicum requirements of their ITE programme ($n = 13$, 2.9%), although in-service teachers were included in research on designing experiential learning in teacher professional learning courses (Radović et al., 2021) and online field experiences (Woo et al., 2023). Research largely focused on changes to PSTs attitudes and beliefs, rather than measuring changes to their teaching practice, and only three reviews reported the impact of placement experiences on students (Kizildağ & Tuncer, 2022; Şahin, 2023; Szocik et al., 2024). The four reviews exploring online placements were predominantly conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic (e.g., Almuqayteeb & Alzahrani, 2023; Kizildağ & Tuncer, 2022). Although they all reported challenges relating to a lack of digital skills (both PSTs and mentor teachers), lack of confidence, frustration, a lack of support from mentor teachers and university supervisors, as well as a lack of opportunities to collaborate with other PSTs, there were elements that led to positive effects with the potential to continue being used to support face-to-face programmes now. These include online mentoring, communities of practice, and virtual simulations. However, as previously mentioned, this relies on a heightened and ongoing focus

on the digital competencies of PSTs, mentor teachers and teacher educators.

3.4.11 Leadership

18 reviews explored Leadership (4.1%), including the professional development of leaders, or the leadership of PD for others (e.g., lesson study, Borg & Finne, 2024). However, none of these reviews included a focus on Early Childhood, representing a significant gap in the research base. The reviews highlighted the importance of professional learning being embedded in school culture, connected to shared values with clear links to the curriculum (e.g., Ambon et al., 2025). However, the evidence base is thin, especially in regard to actual measured impact of professional learning leadership on teachers and students, and more robust, longitudinal studies are needed (e.g., Castillo et al., 2024). Two reviews focused on school middle leadership (Lipscombe et al., 2023; Tang et al., 2022), both highlighting the complex nature of the role and the importance of their ability to facilitate collaboration, mentor colleagues, model good practice, and promote professional development opportunities. They also highlighted the need for middle leaders' own PD to include a focus on leading, curriculum development, management (e.g. resources and crisis management), and capacity building.

3.4.12 Research and Practice

Evidence syntheses about Research and Practice ($n = 17$, 3.8%) were evenly spread across ITE and CPD, and reflect the somewhat ongoing fuzziness of what is understood by research-practice integration (RPI) in teacher professional learning (Y. Wang et al., 2023). 29.4% were rated as either 'low quality' ($n = 4$) or 'critically low quality' ($n = 1$). Wei and Huang (2022) conceptualised their review on lesson and learning studies as a form of research-practice partnership, although this was predominantly coded under 'Teacher Collaboration/Community' in this review. Five reviews focused on synthesising research on evidence-based practices (e.g., Goddard et al., 2022). Sepúlveda-Vallejos et al. (2024) found that facilitator expertise, feedback and reflection positively impacted preschool teacher outcomes, but that leadership, time, attitude and lack of skills and knowledge remain barriers to effective implementation. These barriers were also reflected in reviews that explored school-university partnerships ($n = 8$, 1.8%), with logistics and increased workload two of the biggest barriers to school-university partnerships in Australia (Green et al., 2020). Sjölund et al. (2022) argue that partnerships where teachers are emboldened to use research processes themselves promote the highest level of teacher engagement with research, and future partnerships need to be particularly mindful of shared understandings, provision of resources, and relationships between stakeholders (Green et al., 2020; Zhou & Wong, 2025).

3.4.13 Behaviour/Classroom Management

Behaviour and Classroom Management represented 3.4% ($n = 15$) of the corpus, with all except three reviews being appraised as 'high' or 'excellent quality'. Only three reviews included ITE, with one focused on PST's knowledge of, attitudes towards, and preparation for dealing with bullying (Dawes et al., 2023). Furthermore, only one review focused exclusively on Early Childhood classroom management PD (Obee et al., 2023), with the authors highlighting the

need for more rigorous studies that explore a range of settings, such as childcare and private preschools, as well as research into the effect of PD on educator wellbeing. Four other reviews focused on elements of classroom management, including restorative practice (Starzecki, 2022) and a meta-analysis of the Incredible Years Teacher-Classroom Management programme (Korest & Carlson, 2021), with small positive effects found on children's externalising and prosocial behaviour. Behavioural support training was explored in three reviews, with the meta-analysis by Samudre et al. (2024) finding that coaching, longer PD duration and performance feedback were related to improved teacher outcomes. Three reviews also explored functional behaviour assessment and function-based intervention PD, resulting in improved student behaviour and classroom management, and increases in teacher self-efficacy (e.g., Dutt et al., 2025). Finally, one review focused on behavioural parent and teacher training for children with ADHD (Hornstra et al., 2023) and one on special education PD for addressing challenging behaviours for students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (Marelle et al., 2025).

3.4.14 Data Use

The category Data Use was explored in 11 reviews (2.5%), which were all were of at least 'medium quality'. Reviews included a range of professional learning to assist with data literacy ($n = 4$), data use ($n = 3$), data-based decision making ($n = 3$), and learning analytics ($n = 2$). Perhaps unsurprisingly, given recent increased policy shifts towards using data to inform teaching and learning (e.g., New South Wales Government, 2025), the earliest review was a meta-analysis published in 2021 (Gesel et al., 2021), reporting improvements in teachers' knowledge, skills and self-efficacy. These findings were echoed in other reviews (e.g., Sandoval-Ríos et al., 2025), although were more likely when PD was collaborative, sustained, and clearly linked to decision-making (e.g., Filderman et al., 2022). Although impact on student outcomes was only reported in three reviews, there is evidence of a small positive overall effect on student achievement (Ansyari et al., 2022; Shanahan et al., 2025). However, more robust, longitudinal research is needed to investigate the causal pathways leading to successful teacher and student outcomes (e.g., Choi et al., 2024; Schreiter et al., 2024).

3.4.15 Sustainability

11 reviews were focused on topics related to Sustainability (2.5%), although they were mostly appraised as 'critically low' or 'low quality', with a particular focus on ITE. Five reviews explored environmental and sustainability education, both as a topic of learning and to instil sustainable environmental behaviour among future teachers, including in Early Childhood ITE, where Tran (2024) found that not enough emphasis has been given to it in the curriculum, resulting in a lack of PST knowledge and understanding, as well as lower feelings of self-efficacy. This was echoed by other reviews (e.g., Abdul Karim et al., 2021), and in their scoping review of 638 publications, Blom and Karrow (2024) confirmed that there has been little focus on environmental and sustainability education professional learning. Six reviews framed their exploration of teacher education through the lens of sustainable development, with Fischer et al. (2022) finding that action research and reflective practices can help build teacher knowledge and competencies and assist in integrating sustainability content into the curriculum. Other active learning approaches suggested include problem-based learning, project-based learning,

and the flipped classroom approach (Lorente-Echeverría et al., 2022; Martínez Valdivia et al., 2023).

3.4.16 Education in Emergencies

The nine reviews (2.0%) classified as Education in Emergencies all explored professional learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, and were each rated at least ‘medium quality’. Five reviews focused solely on the experiences of PSTs; three on practicum (e.g., Tekel et al., 2022), one on the delivery of PST education (Kan et al., 2022), and one on online project-based learning (Uyen et al., 2023), which promoted knowledge and a range of skills, including collaboration and digital skills. The review of Engineering and STEM educators by Delen and Yuksel (2023) found that CPD increased their confidence, with school-university partnerships particularly successful; however detailed information about the PD design was lacking.

3.4.17 Interdisciplinarity / Integration

The final category applied to six reviews (1.4%) and related to aspects of Interdisciplinarity and Integration. Two systematic reviews explored Content and Language Integrated Learning. Szczesniak (2023) explored teacher perceptions of professional learning in Spain. Fernández-Costales and Lasagabaster (2025) synthesised 44 articles on CLIL teacher education found that empirical evidence on the effectiveness of PD for CLIL is lacking, particularly large-scale studies across a variety of contexts. Integrated curriculum was the focus of three further reviews, with Boz (2023) focusing on STEM integration in primary schools and Lo (2021) on its integration within ECE, primary and secondary schools. Bourke et al. (2022) explored integrated curriculum approaches for ITE in secondary schools and finally, a review by Tonnetti and Lentillon-Kaestner (2023) found that interdisciplinary teaching is itself a form of professional development, by enabling teachers to collaborate with colleagues and increase their knowledge and expertise, especially in disciplines they do not normally teach.

3.5 What research gaps have been identified in ITE and CPD secondary research?

Across the corpus, 80.3% identified methodological gaps ($n = 355$), 67.4% identified topic research gaps ($n = 298$) and 6.3% did not report any research gaps ($n = 28$). Only one of these 28 was considered ‘high quality’, with six of them ‘critically low quality’, nine of them ‘low quality’ and 12 ‘medium quality’.

3.5.1 Methodological research gaps

The reviews identified 26 different methodological research gaps (see Appendix I), pertaining either to conducting primary empirical research in teacher education or reviewing multiple studies. By far the two most frequently mentioned issues were the need for a wider range of methodological approaches in primary studies and the need for more rigorous research (see Table 6). Many review authors called for more robust experimental and quasi-experimental studies (e.g., Keese et al., 2023), with improved comparison/control groups (e.g., Dawes et al., 2023), comparative designs (e.g., comparing impact by in-service career stages, Täschner et al., 2025), and multi-treatment studies (e.g., Austin et al., 2024) to isolate elements that drive

outcome impact, such as delivery mode and coaching intensity. More in-depth qualitative and mixed methods studies were also specifically suggested (e.g., Bond et al., 2025; Dogan et al., 2025), to help understand not only ‘what works’, but why, how and for whom (LaBrot et al., 2024). One third of review authors also stressed that primary empirical research in teacher education needs to be improved by reporting interventions and research contexts in far greater detail, including what the PD is, the dosage (frequency, intensity, duration), delivery model, materials used, who delivered the PD and who received it, the setting/context and any comparison condition details (e.g., Dinnen, 2022; Shawbitz & Brock, 2022).

Studies that consider the long-term effects of professional learning are also particularly called for (e.g., Rice et al., 2024), as some effects might wane over time (e.g., Jin et al., 2023) and some might be stronger as a result of teachers becoming more familiar with implementing an approach (e.g., Fry et al., 2025). Triangulating data between bigger sample sizes of a wider range of participants/stakeholders was also suggested, such as including family, community, student and administrator perspectives (e.g., Ash et al., 2025; Avola et al., 2025; Donohoo, 2017).

Table 6. Top 10 methodological research gaps

Rank	Identified research gap	<i>n</i>	%
1	More methodological approaches needed	149	33.7%
2	More rigorous research	139	31.4%
3	Longitudinal studies recommended	91	20.6%
4	Wider range of countries/regions	74	16.7%
5	Wider range of participants/stakeholders	73	16.5%
6	Theoretical foundations	54	12.2%
7	Causal pathways	50	11.3%
8	Diverse groups	38	8.6%
9	Bigger sample sizes needed	32	7.2%
10	Clearer conceptualisation	29	6.6%

A comparison of ITE-only reviews (*n* = 116) and CPD-only reviews (*n* = 205) reveals several notable differences (see Table 7). Firstly, 69.0% of ITE-only reviews reported methodological research gaps, as opposed to 85.4% of CPD-only reviews, with much higher agreement on the key areas of focus needed in CPD research. Concerns around the range of CPD research being undertaken were far higher than in ITE, with a lot of reviews reporting high volumes of purely self-reported data (e.g., Ash & Maguire, 2024) and a lack of rigorous impact evaluations to help explore causal pathways (e.g., Stone et al., 2020).

3.5.2 Topic research gaps as identified in reviews

The identified topics requiring further research, as suggested by review authors (see Table 8), were heavily connected to the methodological research gaps. Beyond suggesting more research needs to occur on the topics they were reviewing, 14.9% of authors identified that more

Table 7. Top 10 Methodological research gaps ITE v CPD reviews

Rank	ITE only research gaps	<i>n</i>	%	CPD only research gaps	<i>n</i>	%
1	More methodological approaches	31	26.7%	More rigorous research	79	38.5%
2	Longitudinal studies	22	19.0%	More methodological approaches	69	33.7%
3	Wider range of countries	20	17.2%	Longitudinal studies	37	18.0%
4	More rigorous research	17	14.7%	Wider range of countries	35	17.1%
5	Wider range of stakeholders	17	14.7%	Theoretical foundations	28	13.7%
6	Theoretical foundations	12	10.3%	Wider range of stakeholders	28	13.7%
7	Bigger sample sizes	10	8.6%	Casual pathways	25	12.2%
8	Casual pathways	9	7.8%	Diverse groups	19	9.3%
9	Wider range of subjects	9	7.8%	Clearer conceptualisation	15	7.3%
10	Diverse groups	6	5.2%	Organisation level focus	15	7.3%

Table 8. Top 10 topic research gaps

Rank	Identified research gap	<i>n</i>	%
1	Impact on student outcomes	66	14.9%
2	Impact on teacher outcomes	59	13.3%
3	Online and blended PD	48	10.9%
4	Digital skills training	29	6.6%
5	Use of technology in PD	29	6.6%
6	PD facilitation techniques	24	5.4%
7	Teacher characteristics	24	5.4%
8	Collaboration with other teachers/outside agencies/experts	23	5.2%
9	Influence of conditions in different contexts	23	5.2%
10	Emotions/identity/wellbeing	14	3.2%

research needs to consider the impact of professional learning on student outcomes within schools, evaluating both improvements in teacher practice and educational gains for students (e.g., Rakap et al., 2025). This was particularly suggested for CPD research, although a small number of ITE reviews also identified this as filling a gap in the literature (e.g., Hollingsworth et al., 2025). Student outcomes requiring further research that were specifically mentioned include academic (e.g., De La Iglesia Mayol et al., 2024), social (e.g., Dinnen, 2022), emotional (e.g., Boz, 2023), behavioural (e.g., Ennis et al., 2020) and equity-related measures (e.g., Bottiani et al., 2018). Suggested teacher outcomes requiring further exploration include observable changes in practice (e.g., Basma & Savage, 2023), knowledge (e.g., Shelton et al., 2022), beliefs (e.g., Bautista et al., 2022), wellbeing and retention (e.g., Bond, 2023).

The importance of developing high quality professional learning that is accessible via multiple modes, including hybrid and online learning, was highlighted across a range of reviews. Indeed, only 19 of the 48 reviews that called for more research on the impact of ‘Online and blended PD’ were categorised as either being about ‘Blended/Online Learning’ or ‘Educational Technology’, identifying it as a cross-cutting need across thematic areas. Beyond merely inquiring what characteristics of online/blended PD are preferred by teachers or whether online/blended interventions are as effective as in-person PD (e.g., Ansyari et al., 2022), the use and effectiveness of virtual simulations to facilitate rehearsal of life-like situations was

suggested as a ripe area for future investigation, especially for teacher education (e.g., Ade-Ojo et al., 2022). Blended learning was also suggested as a way to combine theoretical and applied components, whilst reducing the burden on trainers/educators, especially in rural or economically disadvantaged locations (e.g., Dutt et al., 2025). However, the increased focus on and use of digital tools in professional learning has implications for teachers to have sufficient digital competencies, which is an ongoing concern, especially highlighted by ITE only reviews (e.g., Prates et al., 2025).

4. Discussion

The findings of this review extend previous meta reviews on teacher education, confirming that while the number of studies has increased over time, research in ITE and CPD remains somewhat fragmented and uneven (Cordingley et al., 2015; Van Mieghem et al., 2020). Our analysis revealed that only half of the included reviews are openly accessible and very few reviews have been commissioned by funders (e.g., Sims et al., 2021). This raises questions about the availability of evidence that can directly support policy or practitioner decision-making, and therefore the transferability of research findings to practice. Evidence on early childhood education is also sparse, with most studies focusing on primary or secondary contexts, although a few high quality ECE reviews with promising results have been published (e.g., Egert et al., 2020). While leadership is occasionally considered, few reviews examine it as a primary focus, limiting insights into its role in shaping teacher learning and development. Collectively, these patterns suggest that despite the growing volume of research, significant gaps remain in accessibility, scope, and practical relevance, underscoring the need for more targeted, high-quality, and contextually grounded research to inform future teacher education and CPD initiatives.

Most reviews in our corpus focused on professional learning across multiple subjects rather than subject-specific training. Only a small number explicitly addressed subjects such as Science (4.5%), Maths (3.4%), and Physical Education (3.4%), despite prior meta reviews stressing the need for professional learning to focus on both pedagogy and subject knowledge (Cordingley et al., 2015). This highlights a notable gap, as professional learning can be highly subject-specific, and suggests a clear area for future research attention (e.g., Crompton et al., 2022). Additionally, there were considerable reporting issues across the corpus: 35.3% of reviews did not specify the education levels investigated by primary research, 20.1% did not specify the countries in which primary research was conducted, while 14.3% only partially reported study locations. Such omissions are a common problem in educational research but limit the transferability of findings across contexts (Gough et al., 2012).

There is evidence of a persistent lack of methodological rigour in teacher education evidence synthesis. This is particularly evident in reviews on teacher collaboration, EdTech, and research-practice integration and sustainability, with no substantial improvement in quality across the corpus after 2021. Many reviews claimed to follow established methodological and reporting guidelines (e.g., Page et al., 2021; Tricco et al., 2018) but failed to do so consistently.

For example, conducting systematic reviews without completing quality assessments or synthesising effectiveness as required. While roughly half of the reviews met basic reporting standards, such as providing full inclusion/exclusion criteria (55.7%), searching at least four databases (51.1%), reporting a complete and replicable search string (52.9%), and providing sufficient details about primary studies (47.3%), fewer than half adequately reflected on methodological limitations (47.5%). Even more concerningly, only 29.2% described inter-rater reconciliation methods, 18.6% clearly documented what and how data were extracted, and just 34.8% conducted a quality assessment of included studies when required by their approach. These figures reveal substantial gaps in transparency and reproducibility and highlights the need for clearer methodological standards and adherence in the field (Buntins et al., 2023; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2025).

The top five most reviewed topics across the whole corpus reflect growing trends in government policy around the world (e.g., England, Department for Education, 2026), namely Equity & Inclusion, Teacher Collaboration/Community, EdTech, Coaching/Mentoring, and Teacher Competencies and Evaluation (as per König et al., 2023). Of the 17 categories identified in the review, seven of them included a greater focus on ITE than CPD, perhaps reflecting a deeper concentration of effort in those areas for PSTs: Blended/Online Learning, EdTech, Education in Emergencies, Placement-based Learning, Sustainability, Teacher Competencies and Evaluation, and Teaching Strategies. However, given that 27.3% of studies identified a maximum of only 19 primary studies meeting their criteria, greater efforts are needed to design, fund and undertake more rigorous primary research if teacher education is to prepare future teachers to teach in an increasingly complex world using innovative approaches (e.g., Heinz & Swennen, 2025).

4.1 Implications for future research

Despite there being a large amount of evidence syntheses identified, this review highlighted several further gaps in the literature, which can easily be seen by filtering the evidence and gap maps¹⁰. In Early Childhood Education, there were no reviews identified specifically focused on Leadership or Interdisciplinarity, and only a few on Behaviour/Classroom Management, Blended and Online Learning, Data Use, Placement and Sustainability. For reviews focused solely on ITE, there was only one about Behaviour/Classroom Management (Dawes et al., 2023), Cross-Curriculum Skills (Rodrigues et al., 2024), and Interdisciplinarity (Bourke et al., 2022), with just three older reviews exploring Coaching/Mentoring, and no reviews exploring professional learning approaches for improving and safeguarding PST wellbeing. Assessment and digital skills training were also strongly suggested as needing further evaluation in ITE. Further CPD research on coaching, emotions/identity/wellbeing, leadership practices and the impact of leadership on PD were also raised as priority areas.

¹⁰ EGMs are available in the OSF:

https://osf.io/3zmte/overview?view_only=162cd00900d447c4958bd146059509ab

As identified in previous education meta reviews (e.g., Bond et al., 2024; König et al., 2023), there is a need for more methodologically rigorous primary research using a wider range of study designs and methods. These include improved quantitative interventions that isolate and identify elements that drive outcome impact, such as delivery mode and coaching intensity, as well as controlled experimental designs that directly compare different PD approaches for the same behaviour change (e.g., DiClemente, 2021), and in-depth mixed methods and qualitative research to help further understand mechanisms behind successful approaches. Despite the acknowledgement that shorter PD durations were more effective for a few interventions (e.g., Basma & Savage, 2018), studies that measure changes in teaching practice and student outcomes across time are particularly encouraged, along with those that triangulate findings across multiple stakeholders. More rigorous study design reporting is also needed to aid replication (e.g., Didion et al., 2020), including clearly describing the professional learning, the dosage, delivery model, materials used, who delivered and received it, the specific setting and any comparison condition details.

Linked to the continued presence of issues with primary research being focused on a concrete set of ‘effective’ PD features (Asterhan & Lefstein, 2024; Kennedy, 2016), the reviews that synthesise them also appear to suffer the same issue. Indeed, this review raises questions about the benefits of conducting reviews of ‘effective PD’ when it does not focus on specific topics/interventions or within concrete education or professional levels (Van Mieghem et al., 2020). For example, although identified as important across a range of PD approaches and topics (e.g., Graham et al., 2024), there is a need for research to focus purely on developing teacher collaboration in ITE. Further complicating the insights that can be gained from such syntheses is the ongoing issue of reporting quality for secondary research. Given the multiple reviews that have now been conducted across various education topics (e.g., Negrea & Gartland, 2025; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2025), it is clear that there is an urgent need for not only researchers, but journal editors and peer reviewers to develop further understanding and expectations around what is sound methodological quality when conducting and publishing any type of systematic review (e.g., Chong, Bergdahl, et al., 2024). Although not developed within the field of Education, the PRISMA reporting guidelines (Page et al., 2021) are nevertheless considered one of the most rigorous standards. Although, they are not in themselves methodological guidance and should be cited alongside other work that have guided the approach chosen. If PRISMA is mentioned, it is vital that the correct extension is cited (e.g., Tricco et al., 2018 for scoping reviews), the flow diagram is clear using either the template from the website¹¹ or the Shiny app (Haddaway et al., 2022), a completed checklist is provided as an appendix or in an online repository (e.g. OSF), and that all required information is provided in the manuscript. Tools such as QuEST (Bond, 2025) can help authors, editors and peer reviewers quickly check whether the most important information is present.

¹¹ <https://www.prisma-statement.org/prisma-2020-flow-diagram>

4.2 Implications for policy and practice

Given the concerns raised by a third of review authors, including previous meta reviews (König et al., 2023), there is an urgent and pressing need for policymakers and funders to support the design and implementation of rigorous primary research that explicitly measures the impact of professional learning on both teacher and student outcomes, preferably over time. Priority teacher outcomes identified include changes in practice, knowledge, wellbeing and retention. For students, these include academic, social, emotional, behavioural and equity-related outcomes. Amid growing political support for inclusion-focused research (e.g., Department for Education, 2026), this review identified a range of inclusion-related evidence syntheses. However, research suggests that professional learning focused on specific student disabilities or needs is more effective than general inclusion programmes and should be directly linked to specific contexts and teacher concerns (Van Mieghem et al., 2020). Furthermore, although there is growing recognition of the need for increased EdTech research (especially in light of generative AI, e.g., OECD, 2026), the current synthesis landscape quality is poor and more robust evidence synthesis is needed. Indeed, methodological quality needs to rise for any teacher education research that is undertaken (both primary and secondary research, e.g. systematic reviews), and reporting standards could therefore be included as part of any funding or commissioning requirement.

Although this meta review synthesised a wide range of topics, across professional and education levels, there were several approaches that were mentioned as particularly effective:

- Active learning, including problem-based and project-based learning, was shown to report larger effect sizes on teacher skills development (e.g., Donath et al., 2023).
- Coaching and mentoring were found to lead to improved classroom management, higher levels of self-confidence and increased job satisfaction (e.g., Schachter et al., 2024).
- Goal setting, modelling and performance feedback have been shown to improve implementation quality (e.g., Dinnen et al., 2024; Samudre et al., 2024).
- Video-recorded feedback has been shown to be more effective than verbal feedback alone (e.g., Klawiter & Sheng, 2019; Stacey et al., 2020), with seven critical activities identified for video-based TPD in a recent systematic review (Tao et al., 2026).
- Involvement in action research and interdisciplinary PD led to deeper research engagement by teachers (e.g., Sjölund et al., 2022).

However, for these approaches to be effective, several elements were noted as key:

- PD that is embedded in school culture, connected to shared values and clearly linked to the curriculum (e.g., Ambon et al., 2025).
- Leadership support and modelling (e.g., Fry et al., 2025).
- Course design, provision of time to conduct PD, opportunities for interaction and access to learning support (e.g., J. Lee et al., 2021).
- Facilitator/educator expertise (e.g., Sepúlveda-Vallejos et al., 2024).
- PD that is sustained over time (e.g., Filderman et al., 2022).

4.3 Limitations

Although every attempt was made to conduct this review as transparently and rigorously as possible, some limitations must be acknowledged. The review deviated slightly from the published protocol, as bibliometric reviews and reviews focused on paraprofessionals were excluded in the final corpus. Due to the scope of this project, the decision was made to limit the publications to English language only reviews, which introduces the potential for linguistic and geographical bias (Bedenlier et al., 2025; Stern & Kleijnen, 2020), particularly towards research from American and European authors. However, to help mitigate this and identify research from a wider range of sources, including unpublished studies, several large international platforms were searched, alongside Google Scholar, OpenAlex, African Journals Online and organisational databases. This is advised, as PD studies that are published have been found to be more likely to have larger effect sizes than unpublished reports (Visscher et al., 2025). Due to the size of the corpus, a check has not been made to assess the number of duplicate primary studies included within reviews. Finally, although a quality appraisal tool was used, it was not used to eliminate research from the corpus based on poor-quality reporting. Rather, the intention was to identify where poor-quality reviews exist and therefore to identify gaps where more robust synthesis approaches are needed (Bond et al., 2024).

5. Conclusion

The findings of this meta review reinforce previous observations regarding the limited subject-specific focus of PD reviews and the incomplete reporting of study contexts. Without rigorous methodological reporting, the transferability of findings, particularly across different subjects, education levels, and national contexts, is compromised. The combination of inconsistent adherence to evidence synthesis standards and limited attention to subject-specific PD underscores the need for future research to prioritise methodological rigour, detailed documentation, and clearer reporting practices. Such improvements would not only enhance the reliability and usability of syntheses but also strengthen their practical relevance for educators seeking evidence-informed professional learning strategies. Lastly, there is a pressing need for more methodologically rigorous primary research, including controlled experimental, mixed methods, and longitudinal designs that isolate the mechanisms underpinning effective professional development and examine sustained impacts on teaching practice and student outcomes.

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(* indicates inclusion in the corpus)

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CRedit Statement

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